

Representation Of Multiliteracies Approach in Student's Academic Speaking Practice During Pandemic h

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Abstract

The international issue of Corona Virus Diseases-19 changed many things in this year, also for learning and teaching model in University. University of Muhammadiyah Tangerang-Indonesia implements a blended teaching and learning at that moment to keep the generation are light up. This research aimed to report the data analysis regarding to multiliteracies as the potential approach to encourage student's academic speaking skill. 24 students of Universitas Muhammadiyah Tangerang- Indonesia are chosen to be the sample in this research, because in this university especially for 4th semester students, they are required to present their material/ project in direct and indirect English method and academically. This research shows that multiliteracies as the current approach for teaching and learning academic speaking class, because they are not only encouraged in learning directly, but also online learning with many creativities and technology facility.

Introduction

Technology has increased rapidly, it involved in teaching and learning process as demanding era and become one of the requirements to show discrepancy among teachers and students. This phenomenon is not happened in one country, but in the world. Otherwise, the use of variety digital learning are advocated to enhance teacher and students digital skill and promote their learning process (Tiarina et al., 2019). As the time goes many inventions to promote the literacy, in accordance with people requirements for their critical thinking and analytic capability. One of the way that Gutterberg competes in promoting reading literacy in the era of 21st century is printing press (Westby, 2010). Literacy as a freedom to represent belief in 21 centuries, slowly but sure the literacy of multiple disciplines appears, such as digital literacy, social literacy, critical literacy, institutional literacy, academic literacy, and many others. Hence, beside of language skills literacy such as reading, writing, listening, and speaking, now it has already developed become multiliteracies (Westby, 2010).

Revolutionized classroom computer and projector exist because the process of teaching and learning academic speaking is not limited in physical classroom. As an advance speaking skill, academic speaking is socializing and presenting skill to help students comfortable in academic oral communication organizable (Christianson, M., Hoskins, C., & Watanabe, 2009). Students represent their academic speaking skill in variety model. They record their presentation performance, and send to google classroom. This way assists students to watch their classmates academic speaking performance, and teacher give feedback virtually. In some digital platform such as google classroom, Microsoft team, and university learning management system (LMS) also used to enhance student's creativity in creating their presentation skill Giving feedback virtually and performance academic speaking also (Balbay & Kilis, 2017).

In line with students' need to foster their academic speaking and international's competence communication skill is needed (Gomes & Coombs, 2021). Academic speaking practice is quite hard for students to learn, so multiliteracies assumed can cover it, academic speaking course here refers to four principles, they are situated practice, overt instruction, critical framing, and transformed practice (Kaur et al., 2012).

Multiliteracies approach is assumed can be suitable approach for students' academic speaking class, because this approach is able to combine variety literacies, and eliminate student's gap in learning (Horarik et al., 2018). So this approach is propose teacher and student's creativity in utilizing media during pandemic (Dewi, 2020).

The research is addressed to answer the research question regarding to definition of multiliteracies, the reason why multiliteracies is important to be used as an approach for student's academic speaking, and the last is how is multiliteracies approach uses during pandemic for student's academic speaking. Academic

speaking needs a special treatment for Indonesian students, because beside of English as a foreign language, English also quite hard to be practiced in their everyday life, except among their classmates or teachers.

During pandemic almost of educational institution should implement remote learning (Ali, 2020), although we knew there are many obstacles faced during this remote learning. To cover those obstacles teacher is required to find a suitable approach which available for students to learn by their self also (Shi, 2021). In Indonesia, pandemic gives special threat for many aspects also for education, because most of students and teachers are need to be adaptable with technology for teaching and learning. As a potential approach in learning, multiliteracies is involved in reflecting multiplicity for communication (Horarik et al., 2018),

Multiliteracies is one of the most effective ways in improving the skill to achieve learning and teaching objectives because this concept is able to stimulate students to be active with the implementation of multiple dialects that teach students as, inviting students to practice in language skills such as listening, writing, reading, speaking (Rowell & Walsh, 2011).

Multiliteracies can also monitor the process of student learning practice, and encourage student participation actively during remote learning because of pandemic (Sternfeld, 1989). Enhance, multiliteracies can encourage students to be able to utilize existing technology.

(Botelho et al., 2014). This multiliteracies approach is an implementation of a scientific approach that focuses on practice and creativity. Furthermore, Multiliteracies can be as an approach that can adjust the needs of students in this 4.0 era, because multiliteracies is able to transform learning model from teacher centered to student centered. beside of engage students to be able to think creatively, critically, innovatively, and natively technology, Multiliteracies also able to bridge the gap that exists among individual learners. Multiliteracies is suitable with Indonesia's multicultural society because the process of learning propose language meaning in multi contexts.

Concerning to the previous research, that multiliteracies for academic speaking has never been advocating by other researchers. (Susilo & Garnisya, 2018) conducted their research in Indonesia about multiliteracies but it was not academic speaking, otherwise their research stated that multiliteracies can help students reading comprehension for elementary level. It shows that multiliteracies is a universal model in communication in a variety of forms in producing meaning (Walsh, 2017). This research presents to show how academic speaking class is represent during pandemic through multiliteracies approach. As known that academic speaking is can be taught successfully without any meaningful obstacle (Humphrey, 2020). Most of research conducted for receptive skills or for teaching material, while speaking practice is quite different to be implemented by multiliteracies, because it should combine literacy practice (Street, 2006).

Theoretical Foundation

English as a foreign language in Indonesia, needs to be taught comprehensively to stimulate and encourage student's creativity and motivation. One of the suitable ways to stimulate them in learning speaking is through the approach. Teacher should be able to find a good approach to teach speaking for University of Muhammadiyah students especially in English education program study. This research, the writer finds the multiliteracies approach as the best ways for teacher to encourage and stimulate student's speaking skill. Multiliteracies as an approach is able to encourage an non-native teacher to be better because he will be required to be multiliterate in teaching science to his students, (Schwarzer et al., 2003).

Through multiliteracies approach the process of learning speaking become more targeted through implementation of multiliteracies approach, (Rowell & Walsh, 2011). According to (Horarik et al., 2018) states that multiliteracies allows students to learn more effectively in understanding and implementing their competencies. This research aims to show and give understanding the important of multiliteracies approach to students' academic speaking practice during this pandemic. Refers to (Cope & Kalantzis, 2013) distinguished multiliteracies in two implementation model, multiliteracies approach and multiliteracies learning. Multiliteracies approach related to

There are 4 dimensions of multiliteracies approach : 1) practice based on experience, 2) finding out information independently and openly, 3) began to develop the concept of understanding the information obtained, and 4), practice based on new information that has been understood, (Miller, 2015a). to practice students' academic speaking, it is strongly appropriate using multiliteracies approach during this pandemic for academic speaking lesson, because as Miller said that students will practice their speaking skill based on their experience, and they can learn autonomously to find information and develop their understanding through designing their presentation slide then practice their academic speaking virtually.

Furthermore this idea can be said that there are 4 stages of implementing multiliteracies in learning ; 1) based on experience; what knowledge he already knew, and how new things he knew, 2) conceptualizing; learn by classifying, or categorizing things according to the theory understood, 3) conducting analysis; students learn by understanding the relationship between information obtained logically, 4) implementation ;

implementing existing learning according to the environment conditions and looking for creativity and creative through new activities, such as the practice of speaking English based on the information he gets from the surrounding environment,(Christiansen et al., 2017)(O'Rourke, 2005).

Furthermore. Rajendram (2015)describes multiliteracies learningwith 7 basic principles of multiliteracies shortness in 2 domains so that the objectives can be achieved, namely: Content interaction between language text: The language used; it relates to the spelling of language, language in terms of formal and informal Habits or advertising: related to advertising or things that are often encountered in indirect form Cultural knowledge; in this section is required to be able to understand the customs or culture of the local people, for example in Indonesia the yellow flag which means death, greetings as a form of respect and appreciation through the learning process Interpretation, covering the meaning is understanding something related to language usage, schemata, certain elements that can be seen and produce interpretation for the reader(Cope & Kalantzis, 2013).

Implementing a collaboration learning also one of the multiliteracies practice requirement, a lecturer should strive to recognize students who are in low ability, both English knowledge also speaking skill and recognize student's learning style(Arvaja & Häkkinen, 2010).Students also practice become problem solver through multiliteracies; how learners can understand the instructions given and try to carry out the task given. reflection and self-reflection, between lecturers and students need to understand each other the purpose of the learning held, and conduct evaluations in achieving their respective goals. Multiliteracies as one of the approaches that can be used in teaching and learning English by adjusting the needs and bridging the different backgrounds of different learners(Kaur et al., 2012).

Literacy development paradigm by the New London Group in 1996 with the purpose to enabling people in using their capability and creative thinking until the multiliteracies introduced as an approach in teaching, and nowmany researchers explore multiliteracies in different name, such as new literacies, multiple literacies (Paesani, 2015). It concepts focuses on two things, namely 1) reflection of cultural differences, and Language globally, 2) a contextual approach in utilizing information and technology media(Warner & Dupuy, 2018). As a current concept multiliteracies is recommended for diversity learners, such as diversity in language, culture, knowledge, and learning style. with Furthermore, multiliteracies also provided a concept of learning which is appropriated with digital age era. Students are able to practice their creativity in using technology and represent their critical thinking relate to the information they got.

Industrial 4.0 has already changed students and lecturer interaction, meanwhile the digital usage is strongly adaptable for remote learning. This condition actually is not stimulating people about readiness or unreadiness, 4.0 generation should be ready to compete and maximize their capability in utilize and adapt the social life change, such as digital and networking. In accordance with that condition, multiliteracies assumes able to boost 4.0 generation to compete and learn digitally and academically, because multiliteracies approach focuses on multi-dimensional capabilities by utilizing the technology that has developed today(Dewi, 2020),(Horarik et al., 2018).

The Study

This study is aimed to explore students' academic speaking skill through remote learning in pandemic using multiliteracies approach in university. Academic speaking is one of soft skill lesson in Universitas Muhammadiyah Tangerang Indonesia, and it should be taken by fourth semester students for 6 months. This skill need to be mastered by university student especially in English education study program of Universitas Muhammadiyah Tangerang, because it can be a personal development for their life skill (Evans et al., 2013). Beside of those reason academic speaking at University of Muhammadiyah Tangerang Indonesia also as a fundamental requirement for teacher training and education study program learner, because after graduated from this university they need to be prepared for implementing their speaking skill as a teacher.

The instructor in this institution for academic speaking can give score to their students with three criteria; low level with grade 33 to 54, medium level with score starts from 55 to 75, and high level from 76 to 85. The highest level of this academic speaking class is 85, this adaptspeaking components for English as a Foreign language speaking proficiency; grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, fluency, presentation skill; gesture, body language, voice, speaking intonation(Muljani & Suwartono, 2020),(Imaniah, 2018).Most of students are able to speak English, but they feel hard to practice some academic speaker criteria, such as gesture, pronunciation, and voice(Wrench et al., 2012). This happened because of their lack of practicing speaking skill among them.

To encourage students in advocating their academic speaking skill, the lecturer requires them to involved in many academic events, such as seminar, conference, workshop, symposium, and many others webinar which could be local, national, or international program. In line with that utilizing of digital technology and practice their social literacy also needed. these efforts not only for their academic speaking knowledge and skill, but also to enlighten their English knowledge such as grammatical usage, pronunciation, dialect, problem solving competencies and social interaction.

Methodology

This research uses qualitative approach with the total population is 88 students of Universitas Muhammadiyah Tangerang-Indonesia. The sample is taken through the purposive sampling with the total sample is 24 students or 1 class from 4 classes in English Education department. There are four steps of qualitative design; (1) data collection, (2) data reduction, (3) data display, and (4) verifying (Sugiyono, 2017). Those 4 steps of qualitative design have already implemented during arranging this research. The data collection is done since January 2021, through online. While the data reduction also in January 2021, with the objective is to filter the data validity and to make sure the data is reliable. Data display and verifying also done on February 2021.

To collect the data, this research uses three instruments, such as; observation, interview and academic speaking test. The observation is done for 6 months to find students' difficulties in practicing academic speaking performance during pandemic. the observation check is list are: students understanding about academic speaking performance, students' obstacle in perform academic speaking during pandemic, students' strongness in learning academic speaking through multiliteracies approach, students' understanding how to present multiliteracies approach for academic speaking online. The observation process also involved the researcher and sample to interact properly related to their academic speaking class, and their understanding on academic speaking criteria.

The interview is given for 10 questions with open ended question and answer to know student's understanding about multiliteracies approach for learning academic speaking. This interview also to find out students understanding on multiliteracies approach and academic speaking practice. During this interview, the researcher gives participant the example of presenting academic case through multiliteracies approach, to recall students' memories if they ever heard about multiliteracies, and to give a surface knowledge about multiliteracies is.

The last is academic speaking test, this test is to measure student's academic speaking skill. The test is required students to perform their academic speaking skill individually. The theme of their academic speaking is related to pandemic situation, such as; healthy protocol, remote learning in pandemic, Covid-19, challenging in pandemic situation, teacher and learner role during pandemic, etc. students are required to present their academic speaking performance (Pourfarhad et al., 2012) supported by their power point design. They need to present their academic speaking performance in synchronous and asynchronous model to show their capability in multiliteracies approach. During presenting their material students as the participants are also allowed to give questions.

In synchronous model, students are required to perform their academic speaking test directly through virtual performance. With this model lecturer will give them some feedbacks related to their academic speaking performance, such as how they use their eye contact, gesture, voice, virtual background, and many others (Wrench et al., 2012). In this part students also need to be aware on their time duration, 15 minutes is available for each student include question and answer section.

Asynchronous model, students are required to record their video performance while presenting the material academically. The duration for video record is starting from 5 minutes until 20 minutes. This duration is different with virtual performance, because in video record sometimes they use music background, and slide show which is spend time also. The researcher assumes through this asynchronous model students feel free to give their ideas and arguments with the speaker and others participation (Bhowmick et al., 2007).

Students present their material based on the situation around them with related to the pandemic situation also, with 15 minutes standard duration. Students perform their academic speaking skill virtually then lecturer give them feedback regarding to multiliteracies requirement, such as making meaning, digital technology usage, participate actively in globalized information (Puteh-Behak & Ismail, 2018).

Here is the picture, when students perform their academic speaking test through virtual. In practicing their virtual performance, they use google meet application and some of them also use Zoom meeting application.

Picture 1: students practice their academic speaking virtually; synchronous model of academic speaking.

Furthermore, here is the example of asynchronous model, as known that synchronous model is one of the effective way for remote learning during this pandemic, because it can cover students and teachers' schedule and assignment (Dillenbourg, 1999). The researcher created classroom for each student through google classroom, and also create Microsoft team, then students record their speaking performance as required:

Picture 2: stu

Those pictu
then their friends

representations in critical literacy and digital literacy (Ali, 2020).

Students also required to record their academic speaking performance, then upload in YouTube, Microsoft team, and google classroom to show their skill in utilizing the social media and another technology platform for learning (Balbay & Kilis, 2017).

Results

Based on the data taken from the participant during the process of learning academic speaking lesson, researcher identified the capability regarding to the outcomes of participants in academic speaking course relate to multiliteracies approach; digital usage, information shifting, globalized soft skill, and academic speaking performance relate to the criteria that mentioned above, (khamkhien, 2010), (Cole, 2009). Students speaking test is counted and mix with observation result. From the interview result, 75% students are interested and excited to practice their academic speaking skill virtually, because they can create their own way in utilizing technology media, and some of their friends can comments on their performance and giving Q-A directly. Furthermore, students and teacher are able to interact properly, such as after students perform their academic speaking virtually, teacher give feedback relate to their academic speaker performance, such as gesture, body language, sound, eye contact, speech organization, body movement (Lucas & Stob, 2015).

Data analysis in speaking test also provided based on their performance virtually. students' level of academic speaking mostly still in medium or standard, this happened because English also in Indonesia as a foreign language, means it is still hard for them to be able to perform as a native speaker and using native style in explaining material and pronunciation the words properly. 30% students are in high level, with academic speaking average score is 82, and 65% students are in medium level, means their average score is 70, and 5% students are in low level, with average score is 55.

This result show that multiliteracies approach is success to be implemented in academic speaking class, because students are learning and practice with their own way, and utilize the technology properly (Dupuy, 2011). Multiliteracies can giving new understanding about the combination of literacies while learning and practice academic speaking. Students should use their critical literacy when understanding the situation around them, they need to practice their reading literacy when deeply information is needed, then should be practiced in writing literacy and academic literacy (Miller, 2015b).

Arranging their experience into academic writing and practice in their academic performance using technology, both virtual or non-virtual is one of the representation of students multiliteracies practice in academic speaking. As a member of academic people, students also need to complete their assignment and perform their skill online (Lo & Jeong, 2018). Students are aware on their duty as a university students, and need to have writing literacy, reading literacy, social literacy and communication literacy, (Williams, 2008). In the others hand students practice their multiliteracies in their learning process through combining all the literacy they have. They need to practice their listening literacy and reading literacy before they practice their speaking literacy and critical literacy through their academic literacy and digital literacy.

As a potential approach, multiliteracies is proposed to be used in speaking class, because it can eliminate gap among students, who are different in experience, culture, ability, and communication skill (Kaur et al., 2012).

Academic speaking performance can be enlightened student's understanding in running the academic event, such as seminar and conference also. Here is their performance how they can recognize their skill during pandemic through multiliteracies approach to practice their digital literacy, critical literacy, traditional literacy, academic literacy (Ntelioglou et al., 2014).

Below are students' virtual performance in academic event:

Picture 3: students' academic speaking test virtually.

From the picture above we can see that students are performing their academic speaking skill with the factual material, as the multiliteracies learning, that the process of learning should be encountered multiple form images, video and digital context as the representation of media literacy (Westby, 2010). The material is suitable with the condition happened, it is pandemic (Cope & Kalantzis, 2009).

Recommendations

This research is recommend for teaching and practice academic speaking with integration with some literacies, such as digital literacy, social literacy, critical literacy, traditional literacy, and academic literacy as (Miller & Schulz, 2017) al suggested in their research. the result of this research shows that multiliteracies approach is strongly appropriate for improving students academic speaking during this pandemic.

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